

On the Discrete Spectrum in a Quantum-mechanical Nonrelativistic Problem with a Cornell-type Potential in Imaginary Lobachevsky Space

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(Received 12 September, 2025)

A comparative analysis of the results on the motion of a non-relativistic particle in a Cornell potential in a quantum mechanical problem for real and imaginary Lobachevsky spaces is conducted. Based on numerical calculations, it is established that, unlike in the case of real space, for identical parameter values, a discrete spectrum is absent in imaginary space. An example of a set of parameters for which a discrete spectrum exists is given.

PACS numbers: 02.40.Ky, 03.65.-w, 02.40.Dr

Keywords: imaginary Lobachevsky space, Cornell potential, discrete eigenstates

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17949742>

1. Introduction

The crucial role of symmetry groups and their representations in the construction of new quantum-mechanical models is well known. It is the presence of symmetry in the original space (spacetime) in which the model is constructed that makes it possible to easily transfer construction algorithms that operate in flat space to spaces with symmetry, including those with curvature.

E. Schrödinger was the first to solve a quantum-mechanical problem in a space of constant positive curvature with symmetry described by the group $O(4, \mathbb{R})$ [1]. His work was devoted to the Kepler-Coulomb problem on a three-dimensional sphere. This problem was used as a model for describing the spectra of quarkonium [2] and quantum dots [3]. Quantum-mechanical problems on the sphere and in hyperbolic (Lobachevsky) space have been studied by many authors (see, for example, [4, 5] and the references therein). Similar problems in imaginary Lobachevsky space have been studied to a lesser extent. The Kepler-Coulomb problem in this space was investigated in [6] by the contour integration method, and its symmetry

was studied in [7, 8]. The relationship between Coulomb and oscillatory problems on spheres and hyperboloids (realizations) of real and imaginary Lobachevsky spaces) was established in [9-12].

Problems in imaginary Lobachevsky space have symmetries described by the same group of space motions as in real space, but their spectra have some peculiarities. In particular, it is of interest to examine the problem of a quantum-mechanical particle in a Cornell potential from the perspective of extended Lobachevsky space, which arises naturally in the projective interpretation of Lobachevsky space [13]. The extended space unites real Lobachevsky space (a proper domain of the extended space), imaginary Lobachevsky space (an ideal domain of the extended space), an ideal domain and the absolute - cone in the pseudo-Euclidean space. Studying quantum mechanical problems in this space can expand the range of possible applications of models based on the geometry of spaces of constant curvature.

The work complements the results obtained in [15].

The work is dedicated to the memory of A. A. Bogush.

2. Quantum mechanics in real and imaginary Lobachevsky spaces

We will use an embedding of real and imaginary Lobachevsky spaces into a 4-dimensional pseudo-Euclidean space, in which rectangular coordinates are introduced, and the equality holds for points in real and imaginary Lobachevsky spaces.

$$x_\mu x_\mu = \mathbf{x}^2 + x_4^2 = \mp \rho^2, \quad \mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3), \\ x_4 = ix_0. \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the radius of curvature of space. Here, we mean that the geometry of real space is realized on the upper field of a two-sheet hyperboloid (the (-) sign) in formula (1), and the geometry of imaginary space is realized on a one-sheet hyperboloid (the (+) sign) with identified opposite points. Equating the right-hand side of (1) to zero yields the equation of a cone in the pseudo-Euclidean absolute of the extended Lobachevsky space, the set of points at infinity for points in the proper and ideal regions of the extended space.

In coordinates x_μ , the metric of the space of the extended space 1S_3 is

$$ds^2 = d\mathbf{x}^2 - (\mathbf{x}d\mathbf{x})^2/(\rho^2 \pm \mathbf{x}^2). \quad (2)$$

The stationary problem for the Schrödinger equation written using coordinates x_μ has the form

$$H\psi = E\psi, \quad H = \pm \frac{1}{4\rho^2} M_{\mu\nu} M_{\mu\nu} + U, \\ M_{\mu\nu} = x_\mu \partial_\nu - x_\nu \partial_\mu. \quad (3)$$

where U is the potential energy. In formula (3) and henceforth, we will assume that $\hbar = c = 1$. In formula (1), the sign (-) before ρ corresponds to the real Lobachevsky space, and (+) to the imaginary one. In formulas (2) and (3), the opposite is true.

Considering that in the future we will consider problems with a centrally symmetric potential, it is necessary to introduce spherical coordinates:

for real space

$$x_1 = \rho \sinh \beta \sin \theta \cos \phi, \quad x_2 = \rho \sinh \beta \sin \theta \sin \phi, \\ x_3 = \rho \sinh \beta \cos \theta, \quad x_4 = i\rho \cosh \beta. \quad (4)$$

for imaginary space

$$x_1 = \rho \cosh \beta \sin \theta \cos \phi, \quad x_2 = \rho \cosh \beta \sin \theta \sin \phi, \\ x_3 = \rho \cosh \beta \cos \theta, \quad x_4 = i\rho \sinh \beta. \quad (5)$$

The metric in these coordinates has the form in real space

$$ds^2 = d\beta^2 + \sinh^2 \beta (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2), \quad (6)$$

in imaginary space

$$ds^2 = -d\beta^2 + \cosh^2 \beta (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2), \quad (7)$$

where $0 < r < \infty$, $0 < \theta < \pi$, $0 < \phi < 2\pi$, $\beta = r/\rho$ is the dimensionless radial coordinate.

Laplace–Beltrami operators in spherical coordinates

$$\Delta_{BLR} = \frac{1}{\rho^2 \sinh^2 \beta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} (\sinh^2 \beta \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta}) \quad (8)$$

$$+ \frac{1}{\rho^2 \sinh^2 \beta} \Delta_{\theta,\phi}, \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta_{BLI} = -\frac{1}{\rho^2 \cosh^2 \beta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} (\cosh^2 \beta \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta}) \quad (10)$$

$$+ \frac{1}{\rho^2 \cosh^2 \beta} \Delta_{\theta,\phi}, \quad (11)$$

where

$$\Delta_{\theta,\phi} = \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} (\sin \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta}) + \frac{1}{\sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2}.$$

Laplace–Beltrami operator is the Hamiltonian of a free particle up to multiplication by a factor of $m/2$.

In [14], the problem of the motion of a quantum particle in a field is considered, when

its potential energy is described by an expression that in the proper region of the extended Lobachevsky space has the form

$$V(r) = \frac{a}{\rho} \coth \frac{r}{\rho} + b\rho \tanh \frac{r}{\rho}. \quad (12)$$

This potential is the Cornell one, since when passing to the flat limit ($\rho \rightarrow \infty$) it coincides with the Cornell potential

$$V(r) = \frac{a}{r} + br.$$

At $\rho \rightarrow \infty$, it tends to a constant.

The choice of an analog of the Cornell potential is based on the fact that when transition to imaginary Lobachevsky space, the functions

Tanh and Coth swap. By requiring that the constants also swap, we completely preserve the form of the potential as it is in real space, i.e., in the form (10).

3. Numerical analysis of the problem of the motion of a quantum-mechanical particle in the field of the Cornell potential in imaginary Lobachevsky space

The quantum mechanical problem of the motion of a non-relativistic particle in a Cornell-type potential was posed and investigated in [14] with the Schrödinger equation

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \left(\frac{1}{\rho^2 \sinh^2 \beta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} (\sinh^2 \beta \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta}) + \frac{1}{\rho^2 \sinh^2 \beta} \Delta_{\theta, \phi} \right) \psi + V\psi = E\psi. \quad (13)$$

Using the Schrödinger equation

$$\frac{1}{2m} \left(\frac{1}{\rho^2 \cosh^2 \beta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta} (\cosh^2 \beta \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta}) - \frac{1}{\rho^2 \cosh^2 \beta} \Delta_{\theta, \phi} \right) \psi + V\psi = E\psi. \quad (14)$$

we will perform a numerical analysis of the problem in the imaginary Lobachevsky space by choosing values of the problem parameters that numerically coincide with the parameters chosen in [14]: $a = -0.52$, $b = 0.18$.

After separation of variables and using the notation $\epsilon = -mE$ it becomes

$$\frac{1}{2} u''(r) + (\epsilon - V_{eff}(r))u(r) = 0, \quad (15)$$

where

$$V_{eff} = \frac{1}{2\rho^2} - \frac{l(l+1)}{2\rho^2 \cosh^2(r/\rho)} - mV(r) \quad (16)$$

is the effective potential, as opposed to effective potential considered in [14]

$$V_{eff} = \frac{1}{2\rho^2} + \frac{l(l+1)}{2\rho^2 \sinh^2(r/\rho)} + mV(r). \quad (17)$$

The wave function here is

$$\psi(r, \theta, \phi) = \frac{u(r)}{\cosh(r/\rho)} Y_{lm}(\theta, \phi). \quad (18)$$

When $r \rightarrow \infty$ the effective potential tends to the value

$$V_s = \frac{1}{2\rho^2} - m \left(\frac{a}{\rho} + b\rho \right), \quad (19)$$

and the equation (14) is reduced to an approximate equation

$$u''(r) + 2(\epsilon - V_s)u(r) = 0, \quad (20)$$

the solution of which at $\epsilon > V_s$ has the form of a wave with a wave number $k_s = \sqrt{2(\epsilon - E)}$. At $\epsilon < V_s$ the solution is a decaying or expanding exponential.

For $r \rightarrow 0$, the effective potential behaves as $-\frac{am}{r}$, and equation (14) can be approximately replaced by

$$u''(r) + \frac{2am}{r}u(r) = 0, \quad (21)$$

the solution of which is represented in the form of Bessel functions

$$u(r) \approx C_1\sqrt{r}J_1(2\sqrt{2am}) + C_2\sqrt{r}Y_1(2\sqrt{2am}) \quad (22)$$

for $a > 0$ and

$$u(r) \approx C_1\sqrt{r}I_1(2\sqrt{2|a|m}) + C_2\sqrt{r}K_1(2\sqrt{2|a|m}) \quad (23)$$

for $a < 0$.

Since we require that $u(r)$ tends to zero as $r \rightarrow 0$, then to determine the initial conditions in the process of numerical integration, we choose the function $\sqrt{r}J_1(2\sqrt{2am})$ for $a > 0$ and $\sqrt{r}I_1(2\sqrt{2|a|m})$ for $a < 0$.

Let us present plot of the effective potential for some arbitrarily chosen values of the parameters ρ and l (see the Figures 1 and 2).

Despite the presence of a potential well (Figure 1), the search for bound states in this case did not yield a positive result. Pfn the basis of numerical calculation, it was established that, in contrast to the case of real space, for the same accepted values of parameters in imaginary space there are no bound states. The reason may be that the effective potentials in both spaces have different dependences on the radial variable. The centrifugal term at $r \rightarrow 0$ in (14) tends to a constant value, while in real space, this term in (15) tends to infinity, i.e., it is decisive.

However, as established in [8], when solving a purely Coulomb problem in three-dimensional imaginary Lobachevsky space (i.e. $V(r) = b\rho \tanh(r/\rho)$, $b < 0$) using the path integral method, as well as when solving on the basis of the algebraic approach in [9], [10], a discrete spectrum is present. This was confirmed by numerical

FIG. 1: Effective potential at $\rho = 0.5$, $a = -0.52$, $b = 0.18$, $l = 1$, $m = 0.6$

FIG. 2: Effective potential at $\rho = 5$, $a = -0.52$, $b = 0.18$, $l = 1$, $m = 0.6$

calculation. For example, in the case of the chosen values of parameters $\rho = 5$, $b = -3$, $l = 1$, $m = 1$ we find 10 bound states. The effective potential and the 10th state, corresponding to the energy $E = -14.91399$ are presented in Figures 4 and 5.

If we do not restrict ourselves with the values $a = -0.52$, $b = 0.18$, a discrete spectrum of energies can be obtained for Cornell-type potential in imaginary Lobachevsky space. For example, taking the values $\rho = 7$, $b = -3$, $a = 0.1$, $l = 1$, $m = 1$, we find 17 bound states. The effective potential and the 17th state, corresponding to the energy $E = -20.927149$ are presented in Figures 6 and 7.

4. Conclusion

A comparative analysis was carried out of the results on the motion of a non-relativistic

FIG. 3: Effective potential at $a = 0$, $\rho = 5$, $b = -3$, $l = 1$, $m = 1$

FIG. 4: 10th bound state with $E = -14.91399$

particle in the Cornell potential in a quantum mechanical problem for the real and imaginary Lobachevsky spaces. It is shown that the result of the numerical computation depends on the choice of potential parameters. Keeping the physical values $a = -0.52$, $b = 0.18$ as in the original Cornell potential, we find no bound states in the imaginary Lobachevsky space, whereas varying these values can provide such solutions. The case of purely Coulomb potential with $a = 0$, $b < 0$ indeed yields the bound state solutions with negative energy eigenvalues.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank A.V. Baran for helpful comments and the participants of the seminar at the "Fundamental Interactions and Astrophysics" center at the B.I. Stepanov Institute of Physics of the National Academy of Sciences of Belarus. The author (Yu.A.K.)

FIG. 5: Effective potential at $a = 0.1$, $\rho = 7$, $b = -3$, $l = 1$, $m = 1$

FIG. 6: 17th bound state with $E = -20.92715$

thanks the BRFFR for financial support of this work (Grant F25IKR-002).

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